

The role of individual variability on the predictive performance of machine learning applied to large bio-logging datasets

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ABSTRACT

Animal-borne tagging (bio-logging) generates large and complex datasets. In particular, accelerometer tags, which provide information on behaviour and energy expenditure of wild animals, produce high-resolution multi-dimensional data, and can be challenging to analyse. We tested the performance of commonly used artificial intelligence tools on datasets of increasing volume and dimensionality. By collecting bio-logging data across several sampling seasons, datasets are inherently characterized by inter-individual variability. Such information should be considered when predicting behaviour. We integrated both unsupervised and supervised machine learning approaches to predict behaviours in two penguin species. The classified behaviours obtained from the unsupervised approach *Expectation Maximisation* were used to train the supervised approach *Random Forest*. We assessed agreement between the approaches, the performance of *Random Forest* on unknown data and the implications for the calculation of energy expenditure. Consideration of behavioural variability resulted in high agreement (> 80%) in behavioural classifications and minimal differences in energy expenditure estimates. However, some outliers with < 70% of agreement, highlighted how behaviours characterized by signal similarity are confused. We advise the broad bio-logging community, approaching these large datasets, to be cautious when upscaling predictions, as this might lead to less accurate estimates of behaviour and energy expenditure.

Introduction

Extremely large, complex and multidimensional data sets, difficult to handle and analyze with common methodological approaches (so-called big data), are collected and produced by several scientific and

50 industrial fields and require tools to facilitate efficient management, visualization, analysis, validation and
51 interpretation¹. In biology, big data have emerged with studies on gene and protein sequences, gene
52 expression, evolutionary trees, microscopy images, 3D structures and interaction networks²⁻⁵. Within
53 global change biology, ecology and remote sensing, the recent use of big data is improving our
54 understanding of interactions between environmental changes and biological systems⁶. In animal
55 movement ecology, using animal-borne tags (bio-logging) can quickly accumulate large amount of data.
56 The quantity of collected data is large due to high sampling resolution, the number of sensors (e.g., a bio-
57 logging tag can include location and pressure sensors, magnetometer, accelerometer and environmental
58 sensors), length of deployment and number of species considered (e.g., more than one year of
59 accelerometer data recordings, decades of data tracking)⁷⁻¹¹. Tri-axial accelerometers, for example,
60 provide 3-dimensions (called surge, sway and heave) of high-resolution acceleration data to obtain
61 measurements of effort and relative energy expenditure related to different behaviours and activities
62 performed by individual animals¹². Several variables are calculated from raw acceleration data indicating
63 body orientation and acceleration, such as body pitch, roll, dynamic acceleration for each axis, Vectorial
64 Dynamic Body Acceleration (VeDBA), (see^{12,13} and our Method section for overview). A common proxy of
65 energy expenditure is activity-specific Dynamic Body Acceleration (DBA)¹². When validated with both direct
66 and indirect measurements of energetic expenditure (heart rates, isotope elimination - Doubly Labelled
67 Water (DLW), - respiratory chambers), DBA can provide estimates of energy consumption (e.g., daily
68 energy expenditure, DEE hereafter) across habitats, generating "energy landscapes"¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Energetic
69 expenditure attributed to landscape features is currently used to quantify behavioural and fitness
70 responses to habitat availability and human-derived risks at both individual and population level¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

71 To extract relevant information from large and complex datasets, the use of Artificial Intelligence tools (e.g.
72 machine learning and deep learning approaches) has steadily grown in importance over the last decade to
73 the point that they are applied in nearly every research field. In the bio-logging field, machine learning has
74 been applied across marine and terrestrial systems to classify types of behaviour performed by animals
75 equipped with fast-sampling accelerometers. Both unsupervised and supervised machine learning
76 approaches, have been used on both data collected in the wild as well as in captivity²⁰⁻²⁵. Usually,
77 unsupervised approaches are used when validation data are not available, in contrast to a supervised
78 approach making use of pre-labelled known behavioural activities recorded. While unsupervised
79 approaches (e.g., Expectation Maximisation, k-means) independently detect behaviours and allow for the
80 detection of unknown behaviours^{20,26}, supervised approaches (e.g., Random Forest, Support Vector
81 Machine) are fast and reliable on known behaviours^{27,28}. Whilst both approaches have their strengths, they
82 also have their individual and shared weaknesses and can be complementary. Unsupervised machine
83 learning approaches require manual post-labelling, which does not scale well with the exponential increase
84 of data volume. By using pre-labelled training datasets to predict on unknown data, supervised
85 approaches can automatically predict on large volume of data, but are, instead, limited by the information
86 acquired via the training. Integrating both unsupervised and supervised machine learning approaches can
87 make predictions of behaviours across large datasets robust and feasible²⁹.

88 Behavioural validation on elusive species, challenging to monitor in the wild, might be a lacking, or
89 possible only on some behaviours and for short time periods, producing datasets which can be too small to
90 enable robust learning. Moreover, behaviours recorded/characterized in captivity may not be suitable to
91 validate data collected in the wild that are likely to be noisier and/or contain unexpected signals due to the
92 combination of individual variability in movement mechanics, environmental variability, and properties of
93 the medium in which individuals are moving. To address some of these issues, researchers have provided
94 more detailed validation data, recording variation in accelerometer signals of animals walking, for example,
95 on different types of terrain³⁰. Depending on the research question tackled, the resolution and type of data
96 collected, number and types of behaviours needed to estimate (few coarse vs many high-resolution
97 behaviours), machine learning approaches might estimate time-activity budgets differently, and hence,
98 lead to differences in DEE values, if DBA values are grouped by activity type (as done in^{31,32}, for
99 example). Therefore, in the past few years, this field has taken a more critical look at the available
100 approaches and begun to assess which methods are most appropriate in different scenarios^{13,28,33}.

101 As researchers continue to collect data, accelerometer datasets, obtained from large numbers of
102 individuals across years, are inherently characterised by individual and environmental variability^{34,35}. The
103 ideal setting for obtaining behavioural validation and data acquisition over a large sample size and
104 sampling years to train machine learning models might not always be feasible in the wild, making inference

105 of behavioural activities and their changes even more challenging. Both unsupervised and supervised
106 machine learning approaches need to deal with individual and environmental variabilities, and the effect of
107 individual variability on the performance of machine learning algorithms is largely unknown²⁴. The large
108 volume of complex bio-logging data calls for continuous refinements in analytical methods to make
109 upscaling processes (such as inferring behaviours over larger proportions of novel data compared with
110 training and testing data) reliable, robust and as efficient as possible. Here we explore the feasibility of
111 combining different unsupervised and supervised machine learning methods to address the following
112 issues (Fig. 1): I) Assuming acceleration data are sampled from individuals belonging to the same
113 population, can behaviours detected across individuals be transferred from one sampling period to another
114 sampling period? II) is the combination of unsupervised and supervised machine learning a viable
115 approach to include individual variability when predicting behaviours across individuals and sampling
116 seasons? As these approaches might result in differing activity budgets, we also address a third question:
117 III) what are the consequences of varying budgets for the calculation of DEE?

118 To explore these broad research questions, we use accelerometer data collected over two breeding
119 seasons from two species of penguins foraging in different environments as a case study: Adélie penguins
120 (*Pygoscelis adeliae*) and little penguins (*Eudyptula minor*). The Adélie penguin is the most abundant
121 seabird species in Antarctica, with around 4 million pairs around the continent³⁶. Adélie penguins have
122 high underwater flexibility, frequently diving to shallow depths of 5–10 m, likely to feed just under the ice,
123 but also reaching maximum depths of 115–120 m³⁷. This species mainly feed on Antarctic and ice krill
124 (*Euphausia superba* and *E. crystallographias*) and Antarctic silverfish, *Pleuragramma antarctica*³⁸. The Little
125 penguin is distributed in southern Australia and New Zealand and its overall population is estimated to be
126 under 500,000 breeding pairs³⁹. Little penguins are high trophic level generalist predators feeding in
127 dynamic coastal environments^{40,41} mainly on sardine (*Sardinops sagax*) and anchovy (*Engraulis australis*),
128 but also red cod (*Pseudophycis bachus*), barracouta (*Thyrsites atun*) and jack mackerel (*Trachurus*
129 *declivis*)⁴². Individuals forage in the shallower part of the water column, diving on average within 20 m but
130 also reaching 57 m^{43,44}. Both species' are sensitive to human disturbance and climatic variability^{45,46}. The
131 feeding ecology and energetic requirements of these species at fine scales can help us to predict their
132 vulnerability to environmental change. To answer the above-mentioned research questions applied to
133 these two penguin species, we follow four main computational steps (Fig 1). (1) We first use an
134 unsupervised machine learning approach to quantify the individual variability in behaviour across the
135 datasets within seasons. (2 and 3) By randomly selecting parts of the datasets, we then include such
136 variability in training datasets fed to a supervised approach and test its predictive performance and
137 agreement with the unsupervised approach. For Adélie penguins, for which energetic validation is
138 available³², we compare DEE estimates (4), resulting from the behavioural activity budgets estimated by
139 both unsupervised and supervised machine learning approaches.

140

141 **Fig. 1. Conceptual overview of research questions and approach followed in this study.** Both
 142 unsupervised and supervised machine learning approaches are applied on large accelerometer datasets
 143 to detect and predict behavioural activities. We quantify the behavioural variation included in the training
 144 datasets used for the supervised approach and test their predictive performance. We finally validate DEE
 145 estimates resulted from the behavioural activity budgets from the two approaches based on energetic
 146 validation obtained on Adélie penguin (*Pygoscelis adeliae*) from Hicks et al. ³²

147

148 **Results**

149 The two studied species feed within the water column, hence temperature-depth data were also recorded
 150 along with acceleration data and processed (see Methods: *Data Preparation*). The same set of variables
 151 were used for both species: VeDBA, pitch, the standard deviation of raw heave at 2 s and change in depth
 152 for detecting diving behaviours; VeDBA, pitch, the standard deviation of raw heave at 10 s and the
 153 standard deviation of roll at 30 s for detecting subsurface and land/ice behaviours (SI Appendix Table S1).
 154 The unsupervised machine learning algorithm, *Expectation Maximisation* (EM), was run first (Figure 1),
 155 followed by the supervised machine learning algorithm *Random Forest*.
 156

157 **Unsupervised machine learning approach:** Twelve behavioural classes were identified for Adélie
 158 penguins. Behaviours such as “descend”, “ascend”, “hunt” and “swim/cruise” were identified from the
 159 diving subsets, describing activities performed while diving (Fig. 2). For *Season 1*, we identified an
 160 additional swimming behaviour, similar to “swim/cruise”, named “swim/cruise type 2” in 5 foraging trips (out
 161 of 107) (SI Appendix Fig. S1). The same additional swimming behaviour was also found in 3 foraging trips
 162 (out of 53) in *Season 2*. On land/ice, we identified behaviours such as “walking”, “standing”, “lying
 163 down/toboggan” and “preen/high flap on land/ice” (SI Appendix Fig. S2). Finally at the sub-surface/air
 164 interface, we identified “slow swim”, “swim/porpoise”, while moving horizontally at the sub-surface, and
 165 “preen/high flap on water” behaviours (SI Appendix Fig. S3 and S4).
 166

167

168 **Fig. 2. Example of behavioural classification in Adélie penguins (*Pygoscelis adeliae*) while diving.**
 169 (a) diving profiles, (b) Pitch (degrees) indicating body posture while diving, (c) Vectorial Dynamic Body
 170 Acceleration (VeDBA, g) indicating overall acceleration while moving underwater. Colours indicate the
 171 behavioural states identified while diving.

172 Ten behavioural classes were identified for little penguins. As for diving Adélie penguins, we identified
 173 “descend”, “ascend”, “hunt” and “swim/cruise” (Fig. 3). For *Season 2*, we additionally identified the
 174 swimming behaviour “swim/cruise type 2” in one foraging trip (out of 39). While at the sub-surface/air
 175 interface we identified “slow swim” and “swim/porpoise” while moving horizontally at the sub-surface and
 176 “preen/high flap on water” behaviours plus one additional resting behaviour not found in Adélie penguins,
 177 termed “still” and characterized by the animals floating on the water surface without any detectable activity
 178 other than a change in posture (SI Appendix Fig. S5). For both species “swim/cruise type 2” was included
 179 in the “swim/cruise” general behaviour for the *Random Forest* (RF) models, because of its similar
 180 biological meaning to “swim/cruise” and because it was identified in very few individuals (see Methods for
 181 more details).

Fig. 3. Example of behavioural classification in Little penguins (*Eudyptula minor*) while diving. (a) diving profiles, (b) Pitch (degrees) indicating body posture while diving, (c) Vectorial Dynamic Body Acceleration (VeDBA, g) indicating overall acceleration while moving underwater. Colours indicate the behavioural states identified while diving.

Supervised machine learning approach: Repeatability scores for the training datasets from both species generally showed a lower inter- individuals' variation in VeDBA than in pitch (Fig. 4). Including both sampling seasons within the training datasets resulted in higher variation in pitch for some behaviours and mainly for Adélie penguins, as "lie down/toboggan" and "stand" performed on land/ice, or "ascend" and "descend" (Fig. 4). The Out-Of-Bag (OOB) error estimated by the RF algorithm (measuring the prediction error of the model) showed a minimal decrease with increasing number of trees for both species (SI Appendix Table S2). Based on the minimal decrease, the model with 1000 trees was selected for both species to avoid any potential overfitting. Pitch, depth, change in depth, the standard deviation of raw heave at 2 s, the standard deviation of the roll at 30 s and the standard deviation of heave at 10 s were the six most important variables for Adélie penguins, with VeDBA taking the seventh position (SI Appendix Fig. S6). Depth, the standard deviation of the roll at 30 s, the standard deviation of heave at 2 s, the change in depth, VeDBA and pitch were the six most important variables for little penguins (SI Appendix Fig. S7). For Adélie penguins, behaviours such as "walk", "swim/porpoise", "slow surface swim" and "preen/flap on the water" were characterised by a higher degree of confusion compared to "ascend" and "descend", for example. Hence observations originally labelled as "walk" could be confused as "stand" or "preen/flap on land" by the RF. The degree of confusion across behaviours was also confirmed with the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (ROC), with curves closer to the top left corner indicating a better performance (SI Appendix Table S3 and Fig. S8). Similarly, for little penguins, behaviours such as "swim/cruise" while diving, "swim/porpoise" and "still" had a higher degree of confusion, and could have been labelled as other behaviours and displayed a lower ROC (SI Appendix Table S4 and Fig. S9).

208

209 **Fig. 4. Repeatability scores.** Values are calculated for pitch (blue) and VeDBA (yellow) on training
 210 datasets obtained from *Season 1* (squares) and both seasons (triangles) for both species, Adélie penguin
 211 (*Pygoscelis adeliae*) (a) and little penguin (*Eudyptula minor*) (b).
 212

213 The overall accuracy (hereafter agreement between the two methods, as proportion of identical behavioral
 214 prediction estimated by the two approaches within the given dataset) was high, above 0.8 (Fig. 5).
 215 However, a few outliers indicated low agreement on some individuals and a slight drop in the level of
 216 agreement was observed between the part of datasets used for training and the part used for predicting,
 217 so unknown to the RF. Specifically, for Adélie penguins, the agreements between the methods EM and RF
 218 were 0.85 ± 0.06 for the model trained on *Season 1* only, and 0.81 ± 0.05 for the prediction on *Season 2*.
 219 For the model trained using data from both seasons, the agreement levels were 0.87 ± 0.06 and $0.88 \pm$
 220 0.02 for the part of the datasets respectively from *Season 1* and *Season 2* used for training; and $0.81 \pm$
 221 0.07 and 0.83 ± 0.07 for the part of the datasets used for predicting (Fig. 5).

222 Similarly, for little penguins, the agreement between the methods were 0.86 ± 0.09 for the model trained
 223 on *Season 1* only and 0.81 ± 0.08 for the prediction on *Season 2*. For the model trained using data from
 224 both seasons, the agreement levels were 0.85 ± 0.09 and 0.87 ± 0.05 for the part of the datasets
 225 respectively from *Season 1* and *Season 2* used for training, and 0.80 ± 0.1 and 0.84 ± 0.08 for the part of
 226 the datasets used for predicting (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Agreement between machine learning approaches. Overall agreement between behavioural classification performed by the unsupervised machine learning algorithm *Expectation Maximisation* (EM) and one returned by the supervised machine learning algorithm *Random Forest* (RF), ran on data collected during foraging trips of Adélie penguins (*Pygoscelis adeliae*), (a), and little penguins (*Eudyptula minor*), (b).

Effect of differences in behavioural classification on time-budgets and estimates of energy expenditure: As predicted by the confusion matrices and overall agreements, the differences in behavioural classification by the two machine learning approaches, albeit small, gave rise to differences in fine-scale activity budgets (SI Appendix Fig. S10-S15). For both species, depending on the type of training used (from *Season 1* only or both seasons), some predicted budgets as “slow surface swim”, “still” and “stand” could vary more than others like “lie down/toboggan”, “ascend” and “descend” (SI Appendix Fig. S10-S15). For Adélie penguin, energy calculations were possible for 89 trips (38 individuals performing 1 to 3 trips each) as sex was not recorded for some individuals. Trip duration was 24.2 ± 6.6 hours. Resulting behavioural classification was grouped in the three coarse behavioural components used in Hicks *et al.*³², “Preen/Flap on water”, “Water” and “Land/Ice”, showing that the overall proportions of time spent within the components and resulting DEEs estimated with the two methods were similar (Figure 6). However, both differences in proportions of time spent in the water and preening on the water surface affected the relationship between estimates by the two methods (p -value < 0.001, Fig. 6 and SI Appendix Table S5). The model with a difference in the proportion of time spent preening on the water as covariate had the lowest AIC (adjusted R-squared: 0.98, Table S5). It showed that, while DEE estimates by the two methods are similar for the same individual, the DEE estimated by the EM method could be slightly higher than the one estimated by the RF method (Fig. 6). As consequence, total energy expended per trip followed the same trend, being lower when estimated by the RF compared to the EM (Table S5).

252

253 **Fig. 6: Daily Energy Expenditure estimated using results from two machine learning approaches.**
 254 Energy Expenditure obtained accounting for the activity budgets predicted by unsupervised machine
 255 learning algorithm *Expectation Maximisation* (EM) and the supervised machine learning algorithm *Random*
 256 *Forest* (RF) for Adélie penguin (*Pygoscelis adeliae*). (a) activity budgets used for calculating energy
 257 expenditure as in Hicks et al.2020, (b) boxplots of the distributions of the resulting Energy Expenditure, (c)
 258 comparison and regression between the Energy Expenditure calculated with the two approaches.

259 **Discussion**

260 Our study revealed that behavioural classification obtained from big data recorded with accelerometers
 261 can be transferred across individuals within the same population and upscaled. Using a large sample size
 262 and including behavioural variability within training datasets resulted in a high level of accuracy (> 80%)
 263 between the supervised and unsupervised approaches. However, a decrease in accuracy is expected
 264 when predicting on unknown data using the supervised machine learning approach *Random Forest*. The
 265 low predictive performance has been suggested to lie within individual intraspecific differences^{47,48}. Our
 266 reduced accuracy of 3-6%, between the models with different training datasets, can be associated to
 267 reduced sample size used in the model including individuals from both seasons. This drop, is, however,
 268 small compared to previously published values (30-35%), resulting from our overall larger sample size⁴⁸.
 269 Few individuals with low predictive performance (around 50% of agreement between approaches) could be
 270 identified in our case, highlighting that some behaviours were classified differently by the two methods.
 271 Hence, individual variation was not completely accounted for within the training sets. Lower predictive
 272 performance could be associated, for example, to differences in diving angles during the descent phase,
 273 leading one algorithm to associate this posture to a “swim/cruise” behaviour rather than “descend” as in
 274 the other. We advise the broad scientific community approaching the large datasets collected with
 275 accelerometer data to be cautious when I) using training datasets obtained from few individuals and II)
 276 predicting behaviours over large numbers of individuals. Comparison between unsupervised and
 277 supervised approaches can help detect individual variability within the individuals sampled. Increasing
 278 number of individuals, data points randomly assigned to the training datasets, as well as number of
 279 variables could improve model accuracy but at the cost of making models increasingly slow and memory

280 hungry. Implementing feedback mechanisms and further parallelisation of machine learning tasks would be
281 a step towards more efficient management of these increasingly large datasets.

282 One of the main aims in ecology is to understand the behavior and physiology of, and environmental
283 conditions experienced by animals as they move through and interact with their environment. The use of
284 bio-logging technology has allowed researchers to observe and quantify behaviours of species difficult to
285 monitor otherwise. It is, however, difficult to obtain behavioural validation on species' behaviours and
286 variations. Although camera recorders are beginning to be widely used to validate behaviours, they usually
287 collect data for short periods of time and on a few individuals, still not capturing inter-individual variability.
288 Moreover, for the specific case of underwater images, data are affected by light and water turbidity and are
289 still difficult to process automatically⁴⁹. The use of deep learning techniques is making it easier and faster
290 to extract information from images⁵⁰. The variables used in our models have been validated for predicting
291 hunting behaviour in similar species⁵¹.

292 Signal overlap across similar behaviours (such as subsurface swimming behaviours in our case) and class
293 imbalance (as some behaviours might be under-represented within the training datasets), might
294 confuse^{28,52} and lead to disagreement between approaches used. Information on behaviours collected
295 from deployments using camera loggers combined with accelerometer tags could help clarify and deal with
296 confusion between some behavioural classes. Penguins are elusive species, moving in different habitats
297 (land, ice, underwater) and dynamic environmental conditions. Furthermore, the two species considered in
298 this study are marine predators foraging on lower trophic levels (e.g. feeding on fish and krill). Their
299 behavioural variation as a result of encountered environmental conditions (e.g. prey availability) makes
300 them sentinels of climate and ecosystem changes⁵³ emphasizing the need to monitor their behaviour and
301 understand how individuals modify it. Adélie penguins showed more inter-variability in behaviour than little
302 penguins. However, for both species, predictions from models trained on data from both seasons showed
303 similar agreement scores to the predictions made by models trained on data from a single season.
304 Species, types of behaviour performed, and environmental conditions can shape the degree of variability
305 recorded^{54–58}. Changes in sea-ice conditions (as in extent and characteristics, for example), might lead
306 Adélie penguins to move differently⁵⁹ and perhaps show high variability in behaviour. On a broader
307 perspective, body conditions, age and changes in prey type and pursuing tactics, for example, can lead to
308 changes in underwater movements, thereby affecting individual fitness (survival and reproduction)^{59–61}. By
309 implementing machine learning approaches able to analyse the vast amount of data collected with bio-
310 logging devices recording high-resolution movements, it would be possible to start assessing the effect of
311 environmental variability on individuals' behaviours and energetics.

312 In bio-logging and movement ecology, analyses on behavioural variation linked to environmental
313 conditions are carried out primarily on location data, which currently constitute the most extensive animal
314 movement dataset in terms of the number of individuals and species tracked⁵⁵. Accelerometer datasets are
315 also becoming suitable for these analyses⁶². However, differences in tag attachments across multiple
316 sampling seasons (due to different researchers attaching the loggers, to double tagging experiments or tag
317 positions) can cause discrepancies in accelerometer-derived variables, resulting in variability in the
318 recorded behaviour^{12,63,64}. We used pitch and VeDBA as candidates for body position and body motion.
319 We accounted for possible differences in tag attachment by adjusting pitch values considering the
320 subsurface slow swim/swim as the most common behaviour from which the tag “*null position*” could be
321 identified. Standardizing accelerometer data across sampling seasons will help identify the effects of
322 individual variability, and different environmental conditions on both animal behaviours and energy
323 expenditure⁶⁴.

324 Acceleration-based proxies for energy expenditure can provide new insights in optimal behavioural and
325 evolutionary foraging theory, fitness and survival-related consequences of changes in energy
326 expenditure^{12,65–67}. It can potentially be used to explain how large-scale patterns at population levels may
327 arise. An increasing amount of studies show that dynamic body acceleration, activity-specific dynamic
328 body acceleration and activity budgets derived by accelerometer tags can predict energy expenditure, as
329 measured via doubly labelled water in free-living animals^{16,32,68,69}. Depending on the relationship found, as
330 in number, type and resolution of behaviours estimated, the formulas linking accelerometer derived metrics
331 with energy expenditure might be sensitive to different time budgets estimated via other methods. In our
332 case, some of the fine-scale behavioural classes were grouped in coarser categories, leading to minimal
333 differences in coarse time budgets and energy expenditure estimates. For Adélie penguins, our daily
334 energy expenditure values predicted for *Season 1* fell within the range of values validated for *Season 2*,

335 despite the use of slightly different behavioural classification methods³². Also the estimates for the total
336 energy expended per trip fall within the range presented in Balance *et al*⁷⁰. However, this might not always
337 be the case. We advise caution when using and mixing machine learning approaches to predict
338 behaviours and energy expenditure, as this might cause variation in the resulting energy estimations.

339 Behavioural classification methods, used in ecology and bio-logging fields, based on a good understanding
340 and careful examination of the acceleration signals can help improving computational time and accuracy of
341 approaches used. Both unsupervised and supervised machine learning approaches applied to
342 accelerometer data can provide insights into the behavioural ecology of wild animals from different
343 perspectives but come with both benefits and costs. The unsupervised machine learning approach
344 *Expectation Maximisation* allowed us to independently estimate behaviours for single individuals without
345 using a priori knowledge of types of behaviour performed. Checking the behavioural classification of single
346 foraging trips can be, however, time consuming and might lead to misinterpretation with increased
347 behavioural complexity. The supervised machine learning approach, *Random Forest*, allowed us to
348 upscale our analysis, build and test large training datasets across the two species sampling from the
349 variability of behaviours available within our datasets. Random Forest, in fact, allows for quantification of
350 the uncertainty around each estimated behaviour by means of confusion matrices. While computational
351 speed was gained, it led to a potential loss of information on individual variability. These aspects are of
352 vital importance when using behavioural classification's model outputs for testing theories on animals'
353 fitness, energetics, and behavioural adaptation, as well as for informing conservation research.

354 Finally, training datasets accounting for behavioural variability could be applied to increasingly larger
355 databases and/or used for real-time processing of accelerometer data on board of bio-logging devices to
356 facilitate transmission via satellite systems²⁷. While our framework has been tested on two penguin
357 species, it is transferable to other species and systems. Methodological advances in computer science are
358 allowing ecologists to handle and analyse large datasets more efficiently, but interpretation and
359 transferability of results are tasks that need improvements. Refining the methodological applications calls
360 for more integration between ecology and data science fields, along with standardizing the heterogeneous
361 datasets collected, upscaling both data collection and analysis and interpretation of complex ecological
362 patterns.

363

364 **Methods**

365 *Ethics Statement:* Field work protocol for both species was approved by the Terres Australes et
366 Antarctiques Francaises (TAAF), the French regional ethic committee 54 for the Antarctic-based studies,
367 and the ethics committee of the Phillip Island Nature Park Animal Experimentation Committee with a
368 research permit issued by the Department of Environment, Land, Water and Planning of Victoria, Australia.
369 All experiments were performed in accordance with relevant guidelines and regulations.

370 *Data collection:* Adélie penguins (*Pygoscelis adeliae*) were studied at the colony on Ile des Pétreils, at the
371 Dumont d'Urville station, in Terre Adélie, East Antarctica (66°40' S; 140°01' E), over two breeding
372 seasons, 2019-2020 (*Season 1, reference season*) and 2018-2019 (*Season 2, testing season*). The birds
373 that we considered were breeders during the chick guarding stage, in which one parent guards the chicks
374 on the nest while the other is foraging at sea to bring food back to its offspring. Only one member of a pair
375 was captured on or when leaving the nest, when both adults were attending the nest before/during a
376 changeover. Little penguins (*Eudyptula minor*) were studied at Penguin Parade® on Phillip Island, Victoria,
377 Australia (38° 31' S, 145° 09' E). Birds considered were breeding in artificial nest boxes and were sampled
378 across incubation, guard and post-guard stages over two breeding seasons, 2020-2021 (*Season 1,*
379 *reference season*) and 2019-2020 (*Season 2, testing season*). For both species, data-loggers (Axy-Trek,
380 Technosmart, Italy, 40 x 20 x 8 mm, 14 g) were attached to the central dorsal region of the bird⁷¹. The
381 loggers continuously sampled tri-axial acceleration at 100 Hz for Adélie penguins and 25Hz for Little
382 penguins, as well as pressure (in millibars) at 1 Hz and GPS locations (for Adélie penguins: 60 sec; for
383 little penguins in 2019-2020 300 sec during incubation, 10 sec during guard and 60 sec during post guard,
384 and in 2020-2021 30, 60 and 300 sec during incubation, 10 sec during guard and 60 sec during post
385 guard). GPS locations were only used during data preparation.

386 *Data preparation:* Acceleration data were checked and subsampled at 25 Hz, to be able to compare the
387 two species across the analysis. Raw acceleration data are recorded over three axes: surge (back-forward

388 acceleration), sway (lateral acceleration) and heave (dorso-ventral acceleration). Using a 2 sec running
389 mean over the raw acceleration signals for both species, we first calculated static acceleration, providing a
390 measure of the angle of the instrumented animals. The time window applied for the running mean was
391 arbitrarily chosen based on Shepard et al.⁷² as a compromise to reduce noise and avoid masking
392 behaviourally driven signals. By subtracting the static acceleration values from the raw values, we
393 calculated dynamic acceleration for the three axes, measuring the change in velocity due to animal body
394 motion. From the static and dynamic acceleration, vertical body orientation (pitch), lateral body orientation
395 (roll), and Vectorial Dynamic Body Acceleration (VeDBA) were then calculated, following Hicks et al.³²; but
396 see also R code. It was assumed that different behaviours could be performed at different temporal
397 resolutions²⁰. Hence the following additional variables were also calculated: standard deviation of the raw
398 acceleration values from the three axes over a running mean of 2, 10, 30 and 60 s, standard deviation of
399 roll over 30 s and standard deviation of pitch and VeDBA over 60 s.

400 Pressure in millibars was converted to water depth (m) by subtracting the mode of the pressure distribution
401 from the raw pressure and dividing by hundred. According to the resolution of the loggers and waves at the
402 surface, only dives > 1 m and > 2 m, respectively, for Little and Adélie penguins, were considered diving
403 behaviour^{32,73}. Depth change rate was also calculated. Single versus multiple foraging trips were then
404 defined by looking at GPS locations, depth, pitch, and temperature channels to detect when the animals
405 were first entering the sea and when they were back at the colony. For Adélie penguins, we obtained 107
406 foraging trips (47 individuals) for *Season 1* and 53 foraging trips (48 individuals) for *Season 2*. For little
407 penguins, we obtained 59 foraging trips (53 individuals) for *Season 1* and 39 foraging trips (38 individuals)
408 for *Season 2*. Data analysis was performed in R version 4.0.4⁷⁴ on a processor of 3 GHz, 10-Cores and
409 128 GB of RAM. Distributions are presented as mean \pm sd.

410 *Unsupervised machine learning approach*: Both species can perform several behaviours while moving in
411 the wild. Specifically: “walk”, “stand”, “lie down”, “tobogganing” while on land (ice for Adélie penguins only),
412 slow swim, preen, swim or porpoising at the subsurface level and ultimately descend, ascend, hunt and
413 swim/cruise while diving⁷⁵. To be able to detect these behaviours without a priori knowledge available, we
414 followed the approach implemented in ²⁰, which used the unsupervised machine learning algorithm
415 “Expectation Maximisation”, (hereafter EM). The algorithm is implemented in the R package “*Rmixmod*”⁷⁶
416 performing clustering analysis fitting a mixture model of multivariate Gaussian or multinomial components
417 to given data. The algorithm selects an initial setting for the parameters, denoted h . Given a joint
418 distribution over observed variables X and latent variables Z , governed by the chosen parameters, the
419 algorithm maximises the likelihood function. The values of the latent variables in Z are given by the
420 posterior distribution considering the expected value of the log-likelihood under the posterior distribution of
421 the latent variable. In the Mstep, the algorithm evaluates h_{new} , checking for convergence of either the log-
422 likelihood or the parameter values. If the convergence criterion is not satisfied, the algorithm returns to
423 select the initial settings for the parameters recalculating h ^{20,77}.

424 We have simplified the analytical procedure given the animals move in different dimensions (horizontal, as
425 space, and vertical, as depth) and environments (land/ice and water). Foraging trips were split into coarse
426 subsets representing when the animals were on ice (for Adélie only), at the water surface and diving,
427 according to rules considering pitch (i.e. > 60 degrees to detect a penguin walking), and/or temperature
428 (generally > 0°C °C when walking on ice) and depth as mentioned above (see R code and³²). The subsets
429 were then visually checked for potential errors. For each subset (2 or 3 per foraging trip, whether ice/land
430 events were detected or not), variables were scaled and centered and the EM was randomly initialised by
431 setting “*random*” within the “*mixmodStrategy*” function. Initialisation from a random position is a standard
432 way to initialise the EM algorithm. This random initial position is obtained by choosing at random centres in
433 the dataset. Based on the knowledge of the behavioural ecology of the species, EM runs for the diving
434 subset were set to detect a minimum of three behavioural clusters and a maximum of eight. EM runs for
435 the subsurface and ice subsets were set to detect two to five behavioural clusters. If only subsurface or ice
436 events were detected, EM runs were set to run to detect from two to eight behavioural clusters. Variables
437 fed in the algorithm were selected following an iterative approach consisting of considering the general
438 knowledge of the environments where the data were collected, the general behaviours known about the
439 study species (walk, preen and dive) and the statistical properties of the variables calculated²⁰, but see
440 also *Results* section. Foraging trips for each individual and season were run separately, and all
441 behavioural clustering combinations recorded. Resulting clusters from each foraging trip analysed with the

442 EM algorithm were visually assessed and associated to a behavioural class summarising the general
443 behaviour performed (i.e., “descend”, “hunt”, “walk”).

444 Supervised machine learning approach: A set number of observations for each behavioural cluster was
445 randomly drawn from each foraging trip to prepare the training dataset for the supervised machine learning
446 approach. Only the Little penguins’ dataset had recordings across different breeding stages. Breeding is
447 not synchronized in this species and dive parameters overlap between breeding stages⁷⁸, hence each
448 foraging trip had the same probability to be sampled. The number of sampled observations was selected
449 as the minimum between half of the observations from the smallest behavioural cluster and 1000. This
450 way, it was possible to always leave at least half of the samples of each behavioural cluster for the test set
451 and use at most half of the samples for training. The 1000 value is arbitrary and is only used to ensure that
452 the number of samples taken from each trip is not diverging too much (i.e., each trip gets to contribute to
453 the classifier with similar amount of data). To compare individual trips and seasons and account for
454 possible differences in tag positioning, pitch values were adjusted by subtracting the median value of the
455 Pitch considered as near the surface (values equal and above 2 meters and less than 60 degrees for
456 Adélie penguins, and values equal and above 1 meter for little penguins). As the behavioural cluster
457 “Swim/Cruise type 2” (see Results section) was performed by a few individuals for both species resulting in
458 too few observations within the training, it was included in the general “Swim/Cruise” behavioural class.

459 To test the level of individual variation contained in the training datasets, we ran a repeatability analysis on
460 both datasets using the R package “*rptR*”⁷⁹. We used pitch and VeDBA as candidate variables to assess
461 the repeatability on the overall body orientation and acceleration for each behaviour. Both pitch and
462 VeDBA were used as response variable in two separate models, the reference “group” was set as
463 individual bird with a set of consecutive trips. The repeatability index ranges from 0 to 1: a low repeatability
464 (near 0) reflects either a high intra-individual variation or a low inter-individual variation.

465 We used the machine learning algorithm “*Random Forest*”, (hereafter RF), implemented within the R
466 packages “*tidymodels*” and “*ranger*”^{80,81}. The RF algorithm was trained over twelve variables (see Table S1
467 and Results section) and parameterised on different numbers of trees (specifically 100, 500, 1000 and
468 1500). The parameter “*mtry*” indicating the number of variables randomly sampled as candidates at each
469 split, around the \sqrt{n} max variables, was set to = 4. The randomly sampled training dataset obtained
470 from all trips was split into further training (75%) and testing (25%) and a 10-fold cross validation
471 procedure performed on the final training data. Model selection was done by looking at the Out-Of-Bag
472 error (OOB) and the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (ROC) showing the performance of the
473 classification model and the Area under the ROC Curve (AUC, see R code). The ROC curve shows the
474 trade-off between sensitivity (or TPR) and specificity (1 – FPR).

475 Comparing the classification approaches across sampling seasons: We set up two sets of models to
476 answer our research questions I and II (Fig. 1). The first model, containing random samples from each trip
477 within the same season (*Season 1*), was built and validated on *Season 1* and used to predict on the
478 second season (*Season 2*). The second model contained random samples from trips from both seasons
479 (*Season 1* and *Season 2*). As we collected different foraging trips per season, the number of trips to be
480 randomly sampled was selected as half of the total number of trips from the smallest season in order to
481 account for differences in sampling, limit the size of the final training dataset and leave trips for prediction.
482 For example, *Season 1* for Adélie penguins accounted for 107 trips while *Season 2* had 53 trips. Hence
483 the number of trips from which observations were sampled from each season were 26. The resulting
484 model was used to predict the behavioural classes on the remaining trips from both seasons. This
485 procedure was run for each species separately.

486 Effect of using different behavioural classification approaches on time-budgets and energy expenditure
487 estimates: Time budgets resulting from both EM and RF methods were calculated and compared. To
488 answer question III (Fig. 1), we used the existing DEE vs activity-specific VeDBA relationship built and
489 validated for Adélie penguins using data included in *Season 2*³². The model developed accounted for both
490 VeDBA signatures, as well as time budgets. Thus, it was the ideal tool to fulfil our objective of investigating
491 the consequences of using different behavioural classification methods. For the analysis, we only
492 considered Adélie penguin data collected in *Season 1*. The RF algorithm used here, was trained solely on
493 data from *Season 1*. We calculated DEEs for each trip using time budgets based on behavioural classes
494 predicted by the EM and the RF, as well as total energy expended per trip, to be able to compare with

495 other published estimates⁷⁰. Following the best DEE model³², we also aggregated resulting behavioural
496 classes in three coarse components: “Preen/Flap on water”, “Dive” (including sub-surface swimming
497 behaviours, as well as behaviours within dives) and “Land/Ice”. We included the error estimates published
498 in³² and individual sex which was required for the calculation and assigned following morphometric
499 measurements. We used linear models to test the agreement between the DEE calculations from the two
500 methods. We also tested different models by considering the difference in estimated coarse components
501 as covariates. We checked for collinearity among explanatory variables, as well as model residuals. Model
502 selection was done using Akaike’s Information Criterion (AIC).

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Data availability

Data will be uploaded on a public repository and available for download at final acceptance. Sample dataset and all R codes used to manipulate and analyze the data used are available at https://github.com/MariannaChimi/MuFFIN_MSCA/releases/tag/v.02.Submission

Additional information

See Supplementary Information for additional figures and tables.

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